

SHORT COMMUNICATION

PREVALENCE OF *Candida albicans* AMONG PATIENTS ATTENDING (G.O.P.D) OF U.M.T.H MAIDUGURI

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ABSTRACT

Several species of the yeast genus *Candida* are capable of causing candidiasis. They are members of the normal flora of the skin, mucous membranes, and gastrointestinal tract. *Candida* species colonize the mucosal surfaces of all humans during or soon after birth, and the risk of endogenous infection is ever-present. A total of 211 patients were surveyed comprising 118 (55.9%) males and 93 (44.10%) females 122 (57.8%) of the study population were adult and 89 (42.2%) adolescent. One hundred and thirty 130 (61.6%) of the patient had *Candida albican* infection were pregnant women while 56 (26.5%) were not pregnant but the difference was found to be statistically significant ($P>0.05$) infection rate was higher among the adult 82 (38.8%), than the Adolescence 49 (22.8%) and the difference was found to be statistically significant ($P<0.005$). Thus the information in this study is helpful in knowing the final solution of the life – threatening candidemia and checking out to formulate the control strategy in future-occurrence.

KEYWORDS: Prevalence, *Candida albican*, patients, U.M.T.H, Maiduguri, Borno State.

INTRODUCTION

Candida albican is yeast that lives in the mouth, throat, intestines and genitourinary tracts of most humans and is usually considered to be a normal part of the vowel flora (the organism that coexists with us in our lower chigestive tract). Stanley, (2003).they are identified on the basis of asexual reproduction structure i.e. mitrospores (Thomas, 2001) several species of the yeast causing the disease candidiasis. (Thomas *et al* 2001).

Candida albican the most important species among other various candidas causes thrush, vaginitis an systematic candidiasis as well as other disease in man (Kelvinson, 1992).

Another cause of candida overgro-with can be from a low acidophillus and biffadus culture in the system in other to control candida overgrowth (Jennifer *et la*, 2003)

(Stanley, 2003) *Candida albican* infects the following part of the: Nose, ear, toe nails, finger nails, and vaginal etc. (Anne, 2003).

The most common symptoms when it infects several nervous system include; poor memory, fatigue, drowsiness, joint pain, muscle weakness, muscle pain, confession and severe depression (Jennifer, 2003) systematic candidiasis occurs when candida enters the bloodstream and the phagocytic host defenses are adequate to contain the growth and dissemination of the yeast (Thomas *et al*, 2001).

Also reported by Onubogu (1985) out of the nineteen states of the federation four states are infected by trichonomiasis. Meanwhile, the pathology and symptoms of genital candidiasis in both male and female are well documented (Ashiru, 1985).

A study has been undertaken by others in Nigeria but none has been diversified to Sahel savannah area of Borno State. It is anticipated that the finding of this study will help tremendously in revealing the relationship between prevalence of *Candida albicans* and patients attending U.M.T.H Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Study Area

A survey was carried out in G.O.P.D (General out-patient Department of U.M.T.H) University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital Borno State, Nigeria.

Sampling Method

Every patient that was brought to the consulting room was eligible to be part of the study. Two hundred and eleven patients were enrolled during the survey period and subject to the patient's consent and Agreement. The swabs sample were collected from high vaginal swabs in women patients, the patient was asked to lie down with the use of a speculum which helps in widened of the vagina; the sterile swab stick were inserted aseptically into the vaginal and return to the rube.

Laboratory Diagnosis

Innoculation of Media:-

The swabbed stick sample collected was inoculated onto the surface of blood Agar at 37°C for 24 hours.

Subsequently, it was transferred to Sabronaud's agar at 37°C. After 24 hours cultures appear creamy yeast colonies, often with a filamentous edge on blood agar colonies are small and grayish. Monica Chesbrough (2000)

MICROSCOPIC EXAMINATION

Wet Preparation Technique:-

Pick a colony from the growth culture drop a normal saline on a clean grease free slide and make smear using a sterile wire loop. Examined microscopically, budding yeast appears indicating its presents.

Confirmatory Test

- i) *Urease Test* – After inoculation on Christensen's urea agar, at 37°C for 48 hours. Purple colouration indicates positive.
- ii) *Fermentation Reaction* – Inoculate peptone water sugar (2% CHO) in cotton plinged tubes, each containing a Durban tube with suspension of the yeast culture; incubate at 37°C for 4 days. Subsequently, production of acid, gas bubbles indicate present of *Candida albican*.

Data Analysis

Data assessable were analyzed using PEPI, the computer programme for epidemiological students. Association was established using chill-square test at 95% confidence limit.

RESULTS

Of the 211 patients studied 118 (55.9%) were male and females 93 (44.1%) were as shown in Table 1 majority of the patients 122 (57.8%) were between 18 and 45 years while 89 (42.2%) were adolescent (10-16 years) there was however no statistically difference between ages ($\chi^2=0.60$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.44$).

Table 2 shows the prevalence of candidiasis infection by age and se. A total of 211 patient's samples were examined for candidiasis. 130 (61.6%) were infected while 81 (38.4%) were negative. Of the 89 patient's sample examined. 48 (22.8%) had *candida albican* while 82 (38.8%) of 122 (57.8%) of the population were infected. Infection rate was higher among the adult than in adolescent and the difference was found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 3.84$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.05$). Of the 118 males examined, 74 (35.1%) were infected while the corresponding figure for females infected was 56 (26.5%) out of 93. Although, more males than females were *candida albican* positive the difference were not found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 0.14$ $df = 1$, $P = 0.71$).

Table 1: Age and Sex distribution of study population

AGE (In years)	MALE		FEMALE		BOTH SEXES	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
< 12 years	47	(23.3)	42	(19.9)	89	42.2
12-59 years	71	(33.6)	51	(24.2)	122	57.8
TOTAL	118	(55.9)	93	(44.1)	211	100.0

Table 2: Prevalence of candidiasis (*C. albicans*) by Age and Sex distribution of study population

Parameters Age (In years)	PREVALENCE OF CANDIDIASIS					
	Infection		Not Infection		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
< 12 years	48	(22.8)	41	(19.4)	89	42.2
12-59 years	82	(38.8)	40	(19.0)	122	57.8
TOTAL	130	(61.6)	81	(38.4)	211	100.0

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